

Towards an Optimal Design of Distributed File Systems

Uwe M. Borghoff *

Abstract – In this paper, the problem of determining an optimal location strategy for an individual program execution is considered. In addition, we propose a heuristic approach for the dynamic file allocation problem. In order to reduce the complexity of the optimization problems, a cluster-based approach is used.

To access the data files, a user initiates a program execution. Based on the current allocation of the program and data files as well as the knowledge about the characteristics of the programs, a first optimization calculates the optimal cluster for each individual program execution. The objective of this optimization is the minimization of the intercluster traffic of an individual program execution. Within the optimal cluster, a simple load-balancing strategy is used to determine the corresponding executing node.

A second optimization looks for file allocations where the global intercluster traffic is minimized subject to the following constraints: minimal number of file copies, availability, and storage capacity.

Experimental results showing the efficiency of the proposed algorithms are examined, and the implications of the model for the design of very large distributed file systems are discussed.

Index Terms – computer networks, design of distributed file systems, dynamic file allocation, heuristics, optimal program execution, optimization, performance evaluation, replication, simulation.

1 Introduction

Due to the increasing use of computer networks, distributed file systems have become the focus of attention. Replication of files can enhance the availability as well as the performance of a distributed file system. To achieve fault-tolerant access to replicated files, voting is one of the most popular approaches. Due to a replication and voting scheme, an optimal location strategy of program execution is an interesting design concept within a distributed environment. In order to reduce the problem size of the optimization, we use an approach based on clusters. Nodes belonging to the same local area network are said to build a cluster.

The dynamic behavior within a distributed file system, i.e., users migrate to other machines, users invoke different programs, and users need different data files to satisfy their

*The author is with the Institut für Informatik, Technische Universität München, Postfach 20 24 20, D-8000 München 2, Germany, e-mail: borghoff@informatik.tu-muenchen.de

present needs, makes an optimal file allocation algorithm very useful. Dynamically, the location of the files should be optimized to increase the performance of the system.

In this paper we propose two algorithms to increase the performance of a distributed file system. Compared with the previous work in this area, our algorithms consider a majority of design objectives simultaneously, e.g.,

- the cost for starting a program at some node [54],
- the dependencies between program and data files [2],
- the separation into read and write access costs considering the costs of the request and the cost of the data return [45],
- the impact of I/O-activities of the program on the communication costs [33],
- the allocation of program and data replicas [12].

In contrast to Coffman *et al.* [15], and Sumita and Sheng [52] where a write-all-read-any scheme is used, we consider the effect on system performance of the distribution of program and data files in the form of multiple replicas at distinct nodes using a majority consensus voting approach [53]. But most importantly, we assume a variable degree of replication, and adjust the availability constraint to this replication scheme.

Optimal Location for a Program Execution

The locality of accesses may be time-varying [54]. One way to achieve local access is to migrate the data files to the initiating node. Since data files are often replicated for reasons of availability, this approach is rarely effective. Our approach tries to find the best location for a program execution, i.e., we assign a newly initiated program run to some node. This node need not necessarily be the one where the program was invoked. In a nutshell, if we can reduce the communication costs then we migrate the program run near the nodes where the data files are stored. Hać and Jin [31] present an implementation of such a process migration algorithm based on local process queue-lengths in a homogeneous distributed system. Banawan [3] shows that most of the benefits can be realized by employing load balancing within each cluster alone. We will adopt this idea to find the best executing node within the optimal cluster. However, to find the best executing cluster, we use the following policy.

In order to find the best location for a program execution, we introduce an *Individual Program Execution Location Algorithm* IPELA. For each individual initiation of a program, the IPELA minimizes the expected intercluster traffic the program run will cause. Therefore, a *Mean Program Profile* is recorded for each relevant program in the network.

Optimal Allocation of Files

The *File Allocation Problem* FAP was first investigated by Chu [13]. In his static model, multiple file replicas are allocated in a network with the objective of minimizing the overall operating costs. As constraints he used storage capacity and query response time. Whitney [56] and Casey [10] investigate a simplified problem ignoring Chu's constraints. Reduction rules for the same problem are developed by Grapa and Belford [29]. Gavish and Pirkul [25] and Gavish [24] develop heuristic and optimal solution algorithms for real, life-size environments, such as wide area networks. The survey papers by Dowdy and Foster [19] and by Wah [54] discuss a variety of problems that arise when making file assignment decisions. For special file allocation problems, Kurose and Simha [38], [39] develop decentralized algorithms. But typically the various file allocation algorithms are centralized, e.g., [12], [14], [27], [40], [41], [45], [50], [57]. Our algorithm is centralized as well.

The dynamic optimization is done by a *Centralized File Allocation Process* CFAP. The CFAP runs on a dedicated machine that searches for the allocation of files that minimizes the expected global intercluster traffic. This optimization can support the decisions of the IPELA. A generalized optimal allocation of files to nodes to maximize the system throughput or to minimize the communication costs is known to be an NP-complete problem [21], [48], i.e., the problem is probably unsolvable in polynomial time. A variety of heuristics or approximation techniques have been investigated [11], [21], [44], [47]. To motivate our exhaustive search, we explain in detail how a reduction of the complexity and the problem size can be achieved.

Organization of the Paper

In Section 2, we propose the model assumptions. Here the basic definitions are given and the voting scheme used is discussed. Furthermore, we define the term consistency in our cluster-based approach.

Section 3 introduces the *Individual Program Execution Location Algorithm* IPELA. For each individual initiation of a program, the IPELA minimizes the expected intercluster traffic the program run will cause. The costs to be minimized are a combination of the costs for starting a particular program, the costs for the expected read and write accesses, and the costs for the expected I/O-activities of the program.

In Section 4, we discuss how a file allocation algorithm can support the decisions of the IPELA. Dynamically, the allocation of the files is optimized subject to the following constraints: minimal number of file replicas, availability, and storage capacity. The main goal of the file allocation algorithm is the minimization of the global intercluster traffic. We discuss in detail how a reduction of the complexity and the problem size can be achieved.

Finally, Section 5 summarizes our results of a discrete event simulation.

2 Model Assumptions

The following parameters are essential for the model.

$BD_t(d)$	The set of blocks of data file d at a time t .
$BP_t(p)$	The set of blocks of program file p at a time t .
$BF_t(n)$	The set of free disk blocks at node n at a time t .
$BFC_t(c)$	The set of free disk blocks in cluster c at a time t .
$CD_t(d, b)$	The set of clusters storing at least one replica of data file d , where the b -th data block is up-to-date at a time t .
D	The set of data files.
D_T	The set of data files relevant for the CFAP during the T -th interval of observation.
N	The set of nodes.
$NC(c)$	The set of nodes of a cluster c .
$ND_t(d)$	The set of nodes with a replica of data file d at a time t .
$NP_t(p)$	The set of nodes with a replica of program file p at a time t .
P	The set of program files.
P_T	The set of program files relevant for the CFAP during the T -th interval of observation.

We consider a mathematical model of an information network of $|N|$ nodes. Within this network, every node is able to communicate with every other node via the network. Furthermore, every node is provided for local as well as for remote accesses to the distributed data files. Nodes belonging to the same local area network are said to build a *cluster*.

Let $rate(c_i, c_j)$ be the communication rate (bandwidth in blocks) between the nodes from cluster c_i and cluster c_j (see Fig. 1).

In our model, some of the nodes contain replicas (copies) of our $|P|$ program files and $|D|$ data files. The degree of replicas need not be fixed.

In the subsequent discussion which is based on clusters, we need the following definitions.

Allocation Matrices

The information about the location of the files is stored in *allocation matrices* \mathcal{AD} and \mathcal{AP} . Both matrices are distributed among all nodes in each cluster.

The entries at a time t are as follows.

$$\mathcal{AD}_t[d, c] = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if data file } d \text{ is stored at least at one node in cluster } c \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\mathcal{AP}_t[p, c] = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if program file } p \text{ is stored at least at one node in cluster } c \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Fig. 1. Building Clusters in a Network.

Voting Assumptions

Transparent access to replicated files has been extensively investigated [1], [16], [18], [22], [23], [28], [34], [36], [37], [43], [46]. Bloch *et al.* [5] present efficient algorithms for replicated directories. Hać *et al.* [32] describe and implement file replication algorithms in a locally distributed system. Barbara *et al.* [4] describe techniques for dynamically reassigning votes upon node or link failure, in order to make the system more resilient to future failures. The surveys [8] and [17] give more than 50 references to the literature.

To simplify our replication method, we assume a block-level [9] majority consensus voting

approach [53]. Our approach, however, is based on clusters. Before accessing a data block b of a file d , a quorum must be collected.

All clusters c for which $\mathcal{AD}_t[d, c] = 1$ are asked to vote in case of a read or write request. The quorum size $Q_t(\mathcal{AD}_t, d)$ that must be reached at a time t , is

$$Q_t(\mathcal{AD}_t, d) = \left\lceil \left(\sum_{c \in C} \mathcal{AD}_t[d, c] \right) / 2 \right\rceil + 1.$$

The quorum is based on clusters. It does not matter how many nodes in a cluster possess a data file – all clusters possessing at least one such node have the same vote. But, what does “ask a cluster to vote” mean? Every cluster is controlled by a cluster-local administrator. This administrator could be a centralized process or a process which is distributed among all nodes in the cluster. If a cluster is asked to vote, this leads to a task within the administrator process. It carries out the quorum request of its cluster and answers with the information expected. Typically, this information is the version number of the data block to be accessed. If there exists more than one replica of a particular data file in a cluster, the administrator is responsible for the consistency of all these replicas. Let the update strategy within a cluster be *write-all-read-any*. Since we do not expect many replicas in a single cluster, this update strategy works quite right. Now we know, how consistency is achieved within a cluster. Next we describe, how consistency is achieved among the clusters.

Our main goal is the consistency of all data files. A crash renders the node’s data file temporarily or permanently inaccessible, while communication link failures result in messages to be lost.

Consistency

The set of data files D is said to be *consistent* at a time t , if

$$\forall d \in D \forall b \in BD_t(d) : |CD_t(d, b)| \geq Q_t(\mathcal{AD}_t, d).$$

Every time a majority of blocks is up-to-date, the data files are consistent.

3 Optimal Location for a Program Execution

To access data files, a user initiates the execution of a program file at an *initiating* node n_i . The program file must be loaded from some node $n_p \in NP_t(p)$ and be executed at a node n_x . The node n_x is called *executing* node. As soon as the program code is loaded at an executing node, the program carries out all data file accesses. Note that, since programs are interactive, it follows that a program-typical amount of input and/or output material must be exchanged between the initiating node and the program executing node.

Thus, the main goal is to find an optimal executing node for a new initiation of a program.

There exists a wide range of possible objectives. The *Individual Program Execution Location Algorithm* IPELA has the objective to minimize the intercluster traffic caused by an individual program execution.

Intercluster traffic can be caused by

- loading the program code.
If no replica of the program is stored at the local cluster, the program file must be loaded over intercluster links.
- data file accesses.
If there are remote data file replicas, all quorum requests are transmitted to them. If a local replica is obsolete, a remote up-to-date replica is read.
Of course, write requests can lead to intercluster traffic.
- the I/O-traffic.
Sometimes, the IPELA will lead to a program start in a remotely located cluster. This implies that all I/O-traffic between the initiating node and the executing node is transferred over intercluster links.

The result of an IPELA optimization is the optimal cluster c_x^* for a program execution. Within this cluster, we will find a node n_x^* at which the program will be executed.

This approach deserves some definitions.

BR The set of blocks that must be exchanged between the program executing node and the data file possessing nodes during a single read access.

It contains the request, the reply, the requested data block itself, and all acks.

BW The set of blocks that must be exchanged between the program executing node and the data file possessing nodes during a single write access.

It contains all the information necessary for the transaction within the multiple copy update as well as the data block.

BP The set of blocks that must be exchanged between the program file possessing node and the program executing node. It contains all the information necessary for the remote execution, but not the blocks of the program file itself.

BQ The set of blocks that must be exchanged during a quorum request, i.e., version number, acks, etc.

Mean Program Profile

In our model, all program runs are monitored and their mean access and I/O-profile – referred to as *Mean Program Profile* MPP – is stored. MPP is the mean information about the characteristics of the program runs.

This information is held in the following data structure.

```

type mpp = array[1..|P|] of record
  input: integer;
  output: integer;
  read = array[1..|D|] of integer;
  write = array[1..|D|] of integer end;
var MPP: mpp

```

Semantics: MPP[p].input and MPP[p].output are the average amount of I/O (in blocks) which program p causes to be exchanged.

MPP[p].read[d] and MPP[p].write[d] p -specifically describe the average number of accesses to the data blocks of file d .

Example: MPP[p].read[d] = 14 means that program p has an average of 14 block read accesses to data file d during its runtime.

3.1 Objective Function of the IPELA

The objective of the IPELA is to find the cluster where a program execution will lead to minimal intercluster traffic with respect to its mean program profile and to the current allocation of the program and data files.

The IPELA minimizes the following costs.

Costs for Starting the Program

If the program file is (cluster-) locally stored, there are no costs for starting the program. Otherwise, all blocks of the program file have to be transferred to the executing cluster. This leads to intercluster traffic.

For each possible executing cluster c_x , there is at least a p -possessing cluster c_p^* with a maximum $rate(c_x, c_p^*)$. That means, if a cluster c_x will execute program p then c_x will load the program code from a cluster c_p^* where

$$rate(c_x, c_p^*) = \max_{c_p \in \mathcal{C}: \mathcal{AP}_t[p, c_p]=1} rate(c_x, c_p).$$

For every executing cluster c_x , this leads to the following cost function for starting a particular program p .

$$SP_t = \frac{|BP_t(p)| + |BP|}{rate(c_x, c_p^*)} \tag{1}$$

Costs for Read Accesses

Looking at the mean program profile, program p executes $MPP[p].read[d]$ data block read accesses to file d . Each of these accesses causes costs through the quorum request and through the read access itself. The quorum request needs an exchange of $|BQ|$ blocks and is simultaneously multicasted from cluster c_x to all d -possessing clusters c_d . Under normal circumstances, the lower time bound for the quorum request is limited by the time needed to exchange $|BQ|$ blocks between c_x and the worst reachable d -possessing cluster. The time for performing the read access is optimistically determined. We assume that the best reachable cluster possesses an up-to-date block and has maximum $rate(c_x, c_d)$ among all d -possessing clusters.

This leads to the following cost function for read accesses.

$$RA_t = \sum_{d \in D} MPP[p].read[d] \times \left(\frac{|BQ|}{\min_{c_d \in \{c \in C: \mathcal{AD}_t[d,c] > 0\}} rate(c_x, c_d)} + \frac{|BR|}{\max_{c_d \in \{c \in C: \mathcal{AD}_t[d,c] > 0\}} rate(c_x, c_d)} \right) \quad (2)$$

Costs for Write Accesses

Looking at the mean program profile, program p executes $MPP[p].write[d]$ data block write accesses to file d . Each of these accesses causes costs through the quorum request and through the write access itself. The quorum request for a write access is the same as for the quorum request of the read access. The determination of the write access time is again optimistic. We assume that the necessary majority of d -possessing clusters were reachable and all of them allowed the write access. However, we assume that the worst reachable cluster of our majority has minimum $rate(c_x, c_d)$ among all d -possessing clusters. That prevents a too optimistic view during the write accesses.

We come to the following cost function.

$$WA_t = \sum_{d \in D} MPP[p].write[d] \times \frac{|BQ| + |BW|}{\min_{c_d \in \{c \in C: \mathcal{AD}_t[d,c] > 0\}} rate(c_x, c_d)} \quad (3)$$

Costs for I/O-Activities

Looking at the mean program profile, program p needs $MPP[p].input$ blocks of input and produces $MPP[p].output$ blocks of output.

If the initiating cluster and the executing cluster are not equal ($c_i \neq c_x$), then the I/O-amount of blocks is transferred via an intercluster link. Otherwise, the I/O-traffic is local.

The cost function for I/O-activities is.

$$IO_t = \frac{MPP[p].input + MPP[p].output}{rate(c_i, c_x)} \quad (4)$$

3.2 IPELA Optimization and Complexity

At a given time t , the IPELA summarizes the costs from equations (1) to (4), i.e.,

$$IPELA_t = SP_t + RA_t + WA_t + IO_t.$$

If a program p is initiated at a cluster c_i , the IPELA determines the optimal executing cluster c_x^* . The execution of program p at cluster c_x^* will lead to minimum intercluster traffic with respect to the mean program profile of program p and the current file allocation.

The following problem must be solved.

$$c_x^* \in C : IPELA_t(p, c_i, c_x^*, \mathcal{AD}_t, \mathcal{AP}_t) = \min_{c_x \in C} IPELA_t(p, c_i, c_x, \mathcal{AD}_t, \mathcal{AP}_t)$$

Besides, the IPELA supplies us with the expected costs for the entire program execution in a value $IPELA_{cost}c_x^*$.

The IPELA must solve a problem which has a complexity of

$$\mathbf{O}(|C|^2 + 3|D||C|^2 + |C|)$$

since

- SP_t has a complexity of $\mathbf{O}(|C|)$ caused by the determination of c_p^* .
- RA_t has a complexity of $\mathbf{O}(2|D||C|)$.
- WA_t has a complexity of $\mathbf{O}(|D||C|)$.
- IO_t has a complexity of $const (\mathbf{O}(1))$.

The next thing to address is how we find the optimal executing node n_x^* within the optimal executing cluster c_x^* . We use a well-known load-balancing strategy.

3.3 Load Balancing Strategy within a Cluster

Load balancing has been the topic of numerous research efforts, e.g., [3], [20], [33], [42], [51]. Wang and Morris [55] and Jacqmot *et al.* [35] survey a variety of load balancing schemes. The interested reader is referred to the cited references for further information.

Within the optimal executing cluster, we simply use Banawan's approach as a reference implementation for our simulation study. For the sake of clarity, note that the best executing node in the optimal cluster need not be the best node in the whole system. The best node may belong to any cluster in the system. However, Banawan [3] concludes that intra-cluster load sharing realizes most of the expected benefits of load-sharing in hierarchical environments such as those found in universities and corporations. Together with the IPELA this approach will probably result in better performance.

For the remainder of the paper we use the following strategy. Within the executing cluster, the executing node is determined through a simple load balancing policy. Our

dynamic policy is based on the observed queue length at the nodes and the specific CPU-speeds.

Let $node_apr(n)$ be the number of active program runs at node n and $node_cpu(n)$ a specific value for the CPU-speed of node n .

A new program should be started at the node with the best ratio of the number of active program runs to the specific value for its CPU-speed. This leads to the following determination of the program executing node.

$$n_x^* \in NC(c_x^*) : \frac{node_apr(n_x^*)}{node_cpu(n_x^*)} = \min_{n \in NC(c_x^*)} \frac{node_apr(n)}{node_cpu(n)}$$

If two or more nodes have the same ratio, we use a random selection.

4 Optimal Allocation of Files

For a new execution of a program, we showed in the last section how the IPELA determines the executing node in the optimal executing cluster.

In this section, we describe the file allocation algorithm which will support the IPELA. Dynamically, we solve a classical resource allocation problem, the *File Allocation Problem* FAP.

Cluster Initiation Profile

During an interval of observation, the *Centralized File Allocation Process* CFAP monitors all program executions in the network and records them in a so-called *Cluster Initiation Profile* CIP.

This information is held in the following data structure.

```
type cip = array[1..|P|] of record
    CI: subset of C;
    initiate = array[1..|CI|] of integer end;
var CIPT: cip
```

Semantics: $CIP_T[p].CI$ is the set of all initiating clusters of a program p during the T -th interval of observation.

$CIP_T[p].initiate[c_i]$ is the number of initiations of a program p at cluster c_i during the T -th interval of observation.

At the end of an observation interval, the CFAP determines in a timer-controlled exhaustive calculation the (sub-) optimal allocation of files. This technique has been used by [10], [12], [13], [45], [49]. However, our CFAP only has knowledge about clusters, i.e., free disk space in a cluster, current cluster allocation of files, etc. Therefore, every dynamically calculated allocation of files is based on clusters. The CFAP does not care about nodes nor

about the allocation of file replicas to nodes. The main goal of the CFAP is to minimize the expected global intercluster traffic.

Since our dynamic file allocation is a periodical task, we just look at the transition from the (T-1)-th interval of observation to the T-th. At a time t_T , the CFAP estimates the cluster initiator profile for the next interval of observation by

$$E(CIP_T) = CIP_{T-1}.$$

Relevant Program and Data Files

To reduce the overall problem size, we introduce the relevant program and data sets for the CFAP. In the subsequent discussion of the dynamic file allocation problem, the CFAP will just look for combinations where the relevant file sets' allocation is varied.

Let

$$P_T = \{p \in P : E(CIP_T)[p].CI \neq \emptyset\}$$

be the set of all program files relevant for the CFAP and

$$D_T(p) = \{d \in D : MPP[p].read[d] > 0 \vee MPP[p].write[d] > 0\}.$$

Let

$$D_T = \bigcup_{p \in P_T} D_T(p)$$

be the set of all data files relevant for the CFAP.

Program files are *relevant*, if there is at least one initiating cluster for these programs in the expected cluster initiator profile for the next interval of observation.

Data files are *relevant*, if there are relevant programs which will have accesses to these data files with respect to their mean program profile.

4.1 Objective Function of the CFAP

For a particular scenario described by the cluster allocation matrices and the expected cluster initiator profile for the current interval of observation, the estimated costs are calculated by an instance of the centralized file allocation process $CFAP_T$ where

$$CFAP_T = \sum_{p \in P_T} \sum_{c_i \in E(CIP_T)[p].CI} E(CIP_T)[p].initiate[c_i] \times IPELAcost_x^*.$$

Recall that $IPELAcost_x^*$ are the estimated costs for an entire program execution at the optimal executing cluster (calculated through the IPELA).

As is seen from the definition, a single run of CFAP for a given cluster allocation has a complexity of

$$\mathbf{O} \left((|P_T| + 3|P_T||D_T|) |C|^3 + |P_T||C|^2 \right)$$

This upper bound holds, if all clusters are initiators for all relevant programs.

The generalized file allocation problem that must be solved can be described as follows. Look for an optimal cluster allocation that minimizes the global intercluster traffic with respect to the expected cluster initiator profile of the current interval of observation, i.e., the CFAP must solve the following problem.

$$CFAP_T(\mathcal{AD}_{t_T}^*, \mathcal{AP}_{t_T}^*, E(CIP_T)) = \min_{\mathcal{AD}_{t_T}, \mathcal{AP}_{t_T}} CFAP_T(\mathcal{AD}_{t_T}, \mathcal{AP}_{t_T}, E(CIP_T))$$

It should be noted that $\mathcal{AD}_{t_T}^*$ and $\mathcal{AP}_{t_T}^*$ will differ from \mathcal{AD}_{t_T} and \mathcal{AP}_{t_T} only in the relevant data or program files allocation.

Every candidate of a possible cluster allocation is subject to the following constraints.

Constraint 1: Minimal Number of Copies

Let $min_rep(d)$ and $min_rep(p)$ be the minimum number of replicas of data file d and program file p , respectively. Default is 1. There exists a minimal number of replicas for each program or data file which is adjusted by the users or the system's administrator.

For an optimal allocation, the degree of replication for every data file $rep(d)$, and every program file $rep(p)$, respectively, must not fall below the proposed degree of replication, i.e., it must satisfy the conditions

$$\forall d \in D_T : min_rep(d) \leq rep_{t_T}(d) = \sum_{c \in C} \mathcal{AD}_{t_T}^*[d, c]$$

$$\forall p \in P_T : min_rep(p) \leq rep_{t_T}(p) = \sum_{c \in C} \mathcal{AP}_{t_T}^*[p, c]$$

A check whether this constraint is fulfilled has a complexity of

$$\mathbf{O} \left((|P_T| + |D_T|) |C| \right).$$

Constraint 2: Availability

Let min_avail be a threshold representing the minimal availability that must be reached for every expected program execution. What does "availability of a program execution" mean?

Mahmoud and Riordon introduce this type of constraint in [44]. They define availability as the probability that a file is accessible when requested by users in the network. We must adjust this definition to our model. The dependencies between program and data files, and the separation into read and write accesses using a majority consensus approach, leads to the following definition.

The availability of a program execution is the product of the following two probabilities.

1. $PROB_p$: The probability of successfully loading a replica of program p at a node in the initiating cluster.

Therefore, at least one p -possessing node must be reached.

2. $PROB_d$: The probability of successfully accessing the data files (with respect to the mean program profile of the program p).

Therefore, at least the quorum size (a majority) of d -possessing nodes must be reached for every expected access to the data files.

Example: All replicas of the program file p are stored in 4 clusters, all replicas of the data file d are stored in 3 clusters.

The probability of reaching the i -th replica of the program file p from the initiating cluster be $prob_{c_{p_i}}$, $i \in \{1, \dots, 4\}$.

The probability of reaching the j -th replica of the data file d from the initiating cluster be $prob_{c_{d_j}}$, $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$.

Hence, the probability of reaching at least one replica of the program file p from the initiating cluster is

$$PROB_p = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^4 (1 - prob_{c_{p_i}}).$$

The quorum size Q for every access to d equals 2.

The probability of reaching at least Q replicas of the data file d from the initiating cluster is

$$\begin{aligned} PROB_d = & prob_{c_{d_1}} \times prob_{c_{d_2}} \times (1 - prob_{c_{d_3}}) + \\ & prob_{c_{d_1}} \times prob_{c_{d_3}} \times (1 - prob_{c_{d_2}}) + \\ & prob_{c_{d_2}} \times prob_{c_{d_3}} \times (1 - prob_{c_{d_1}}) + \\ & prob_{c_{d_1}} \times prob_{c_{d_2}} \times prob_{c_{d_3}} \end{aligned}$$

This is equivalent to

$$\begin{aligned} PROB_d = & prob_{c_{d_1}} \times prob_{c_{d_2}} + prob_{c_{d_1}} \times prob_{c_{d_3}} + prob_{c_{d_2}} \times prob_{c_{d_3}} - \\ & 2 \times prob_{c_{d_1}} \times prob_{c_{d_2}} \times prob_{c_{d_3}} \end{aligned}$$

Let $prob_{c_{p_i}} = 0.8$, $i \in \{1, \dots, 4\}$, and $prob_{c_{d_j}} = 0.9$, $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, then $avail = PROB_p \times PROB_d = 0.9984 \times 0.972 \approx 0.97$.

Our example shows the availability for a trivial scenario. Let us look for a general formula. For simplicity and generality we assume the $prob$ -values to be independent. Otherwise we must use topology-dependent routing tables and configuration features, as proposed in [26].

At the T -th interval of observation, the availability of the program executions is given by

$$avail_T(\mathcal{AD}_{t_T}^*, \mathcal{AP}_{t_T}^*) = PROB_p \times PROB_d.$$

Letting

$$Q^* = Q_{t_T}(\mathcal{AD}_{t_T}^*, d) = \left\lceil \left(\sum_{c \in C} \mathcal{AD}_{t_T}^*[d, c] \right) / 2 \right\rceil + 1$$

and

$$S_p^* = \{c \in C : \mathcal{AP}_{t_T}^*[p, c] = 1\}$$

as well as

$$S_d^* = \{c \in C : \mathcal{AD}_{t_T}^*[d, c] = 1\}$$

yields to

$$PROB_p = 1 - \prod_{c_p^* \in S_p^*} (1 - prob_{c_p^*})$$

and

$$PROB_d = \sum_{l=Q^*}^{|S_d^*|} \binom{l-1}{Q^*-1} (-1)^{l-Q^*} \sum_{i_1 < \dots < i_l} \prod_{j=1}^l prob_{c_{d_{i_j}}^*}$$

The term “ $i_1 < \dots < i_l$ ” describes the i -th permutation of the indices, such that $i_1 < i_2, i_2 < i_3$, etc.

This leads to the following constraint. For all program and data files relevant for the CFAP, and for all expected initiating clusters, the availability must exceed the threshold *min_avail*, i.e.,

$$\forall p \in P_T, \forall d \in D_T, \forall c_i \in E(CIP_T)[p].CI : avail_T(\mathcal{AD}_{t_T}^*, \mathcal{AP}_{t_T}^*) > min_avail.$$

The complexity of an availability check is

$$\mathbf{O}(2|P_T||D_T||C|^2).$$

Constraint 3: Storage Capacity

The storage capacity constraint was first introduced by Chu [13]. The amount of storage needed at each node or cluster, respectively, must not exceed the available storage capacity. The following notation is used in the presenting the constraint.

At a time t , $|BFC_t(c)|$ is the free disk space in cluster c and equals the sum of the free disk spaces of all nodes r in $NC(c)$.

An optimal allocation stipulates that all files can be stored within the allocated clusters, i.e., it must satisfy the condition

$$\forall c \in C : |BFC_{t_T}(c)| > \sum_{p \in P} |BP_{t_T}(p)| \left(\mathcal{AP}_{t_T}^*[p, c] - |NP_{t_T}(p) \cap NC(c)| \right) + \sum_{d \in D} |BD_{t_T}(d)| \left(\mathcal{AD}_{t_T}^*[d, c] - |ND_{t_T}(d) \cap NC(c)| \right)$$

As a result of a CFAP optimization, cluster c is determined to be a storing location for a replica of a file or **not**. If cluster c is freed from storing a particular file replica then **all**

cluster-local replicas of this file are removed from cluster c (see \cap -term). Trivially, each storage capacity check has a complexity of

$$\mathbf{O}\left(\left(|P| + |D|\right) |C|\right).$$

Note, however, that a positive check of the storage capacity does not enforce a manageable allocation.

Example: Let $|BFC_t(c)|$ be 100 blocks and d the only file which should be newly allocated at cluster c . Let $|BD_t(d)|$ be 80 blocks. There is a slight chance that no node in c has enough free disk space to store a whole replica of d . A possible solution to this problem could be an allocation of file d where d is partially distributed among the nodes in cluster c . However, this paper does not address the cluster-local housekeeping.

4.2 Complexity

The centralized allocation process tries to solve an NP-complete optimization. Consequently, all possible allocations must be checked and their costs must be calculated.

In principle, there are

$$\sum_{rep(p_1)=1}^{|C|} \dots \sum_{rep(p_{|P|})=1}^{|C|} \sum_{rep(d_1)=1}^{|C|} \dots \sum_{rep(d_{|D|})=1}^{|C|} \prod_{p_i \in P} \binom{|C|}{rep(p_i)} \times \prod_{d_j \in D} \binom{|C|}{rep(d_j)}$$

different allocations. The resulting complexity is too high, i.e., the model could not be solved to optimality due to the size and complexity of the resulting mathematical program. To remedy these drawbacks, we introduce the following approach to reduce the possible combinations. First of all, we try to find an allocation where the minimal number of file replicas equals exactly the proposed number of file replicas. Thus, we do not need to check whether the first constraint is fulfilled or not. Second, we just look for combinations where the relevant file sets' allocation is varied. Since $|P_T| \ll |P|$ and $|D_T| \ll |D|$, a manageable exhaustive search for the optimal allocation yields to

$$\prod_{p_i \in P_T} \binom{|C|}{min_rep(p_i)} \times \prod_{d_j \in D_T} \binom{|C|}{min_rep(d_j)}$$

different combinations.

Continuing, by letting

$$REP = \max \left(\max_{p \in P_T} min_rep(p), \max_{d \in D_T} min_rep(d) \right)$$

and

$$|C| \gg REP$$

yields to the following overall complexity for our CFAP.

$$O \left(\underbrace{\binom{|C|}{REP}}_{\text{Combinations}}^{|P_T|+|D_T|} \left(\underbrace{(|P_T| + 3|P_T||D_T|) |C|^3 + |P_T||C|^2}_{\text{single CFAP-run}} + \underbrace{2|P_T||D_T||C|^2}_{\text{Constraint 2}} + \underbrace{(|P| + |D|)|C|}_{\text{Constraint 3}} \right) \right)$$

The last summand of the above complexity mirrors the storage capacity check. Thus, the values $|P|$ and $|D|$ are used. However, the linearity in the number of clusters makes this summand suitable.

Modification of the number of file replicas

To check all possible candidates where the number of replicas is greater or equal the minimal number would raise the complexity by a factor of

$$|C|^{|P_T|+|D_T|}.$$

Only if no allocation can be found which fulfills all constraints, we increase the number of replicas for some files. During the availability check, we know which combination p/d for an initiator c_i falls below the *min_avail* threshold. For these particular combinations, we will increase the number of replicas of the program file p as well as the number of replicas of the data file d .

Hać [30] develops a decentralized algorithm that decides on replication based on the number of read and write accesses, file size, and utilization of the communication network. In our approach, the degree of replication is determined through the availability constraint. This constraint is globally calculated for every expected program run, and every expected data file utilization. Therefore, our scheme is centralized and embedded in the CFAP.

To move from a current allocation towards the optimal one, files must be relocated. The relocation of files must not endanger the consistency of the file system even when the degree of replication is not fixed and dynamically changed. [7] introduces three basic relocation protocols to preserve consistency during relocation and presents read and write algorithms for accesses to data blocks of transient files.

5 Simulation Study

A discrete event simulation is used to compare the following four strategies.

- Strategy (1): No optimization (reference strategy).
A program is always executed at the initiating node. The file allocation is fixed.
- Strategy (2): Cluster-local load-balancing.
Within the initiating cluster, a program is executed in a load-balanced way. The file allocation is fixed.

- Strategy (3): Only IPELA.
Within the optimal cluster (see Section 3), a program is executed in a load-balanced way. The file allocation is fixed.
- Strategy (4): IPELA and CFAP.
A program is executed as in Strategy (3). The file allocation is optimized and dynamically changed (see Section 4).

Model

For the simulation we consider a five cluster network. The configuration of the network and the clustering is shown in Fig. 1. Note, however, that the costs of intercluster communication are not identical. Tests with more complicated network topologies revealed that the behavior shown by this simple topology is indicative of the behavior of an arbitrary cluster network.

In our model, the nodes are denoted n_1 to n_{50} . Each node n_i may crash with probability $prob_{crash} = 0.0000016$ (a nodes crashes with a mean of one week). The time to reboot be 10 minutes. If a crash occurs, the CPU immediately stops working (*fail-stop*). Intracluster links do not fail. Intercluster links fail with a probability of 0.0017 or in other words, every ten minutes. Let the time for an intercluster link failure be 10 seconds. Therefore, the partitioning points in our network are the gateway nodes. All nodes of a cluster do always belong to the same partition.

Three data files, denoted d_1 to d_3 (size 30, 300, 3000 blocks, respectively), and 30 program files, denoted p_1 to p_{30} , are distributed among the clusters. Program Group I (p_1 to p_{10}) are I/O-active programs. Program Group II (p_{11} to p_{20}) are data file accessing programs. Program Group III (p_{21} to p_{30}) are both, I/O-active and data file accessing.

Tab. 1 describes the size of the program files. Moreover, it illustrates the initialized values of the mean program profile.

Implementation of the Simulator

The simulation model was programmed in PASCAL and executed on VAX computers. The simulations were executed for at least 30 simulated days and 90% confidence intervals were computed for all program runtime measures. All nodes were operating at the start of the simulations, but runtime measurements only commenced after 10 simulated days. This ensures that only steady-state behavior is monitored.

The period of an observation interval depends on the activities in the network – every time, the cardinality of P_T equals or exceeds 10, the CFAP is activated. Every run of CFAP is supervised by a software-timer (a maximum of 45000 different combinations of cluster allocations are checked). In our current CFAP implementation, a check of a single cluster allocation together with the constraint inspections needs 0.08 CPU-seconds on a

P	$ BP_t $	input output		read			write		
				d_1	d_2	d_3	d_1	d_2	d_3
p_1	1	50	50	-	-	-	-	-	-
p_2	3	100	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
p_3	5	150	150	-	-	-	-	-	-
p_4	7	200	200	-	-	-	-	-	-
p_5	9	250	250	-	-	-	-	-	-
p_6	10	300	300	-	-	-	-	-	-
p_7	20	350	350	-	-	-	-	-	-
p_8	30	400	400	-	-	-	-	-	-
p_9	40	450	450	-	-	-	-	-	-
p_{10}	50	500	500	-	-	-	-	-	-
p_{11}	60	-	-	20	-	-	-	-	-
p_{12}	70	-	-	-	30	-	-	-	-
p_{13}	80	-	-	-	-	40	-	-	-
p_{14}	90	-	-	20	-	-	20	-	-
p_{15}	100	-	-	-	30	-	-	30	-
p_{16}	120	-	-	-	-	40	-	-	40
p_{17}	140	-	-	20	20	-	20	20	-
p_{18}	160	-	-	-	30	30	-	30	30
p_{19}	180	-	-	20	20	20	20	20	20
p_{20}	200	-	-	30	30	30	30	30	30
p_{21}	220	20	20	10	-	-	-	-	-
p_{22}	240	20	20	-	20	-	-	-	-
p_{23}	260	20	20	-	-	30	-	-	-
p_{24}	280	20	20	10	-	-	10	-	-
p_{25}	300	20	20	-	20	-	-	20	-
p_{26}	320	20	20	10	10	-	10	10	-
p_{27}	340	20	20	10	10	10	10	10	10
p_{28}	360	20	20	10	10	20	10	10	20
p_{29}	380	20	20	10	20	20	10	20	20
p_{30}	400	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20

Tab. 1. Program File Characteristics.

DEC VAXstation II RC. Hence, the software-timer guarantees that at least every hour a new suboptimal allocation is calculated.

This policy was a compromise between the calculation of rather obsolete optimal allocations and quite up-to-date suboptimal ones. The use of a faster computer as dedicated

machine that searches for the allocation of files can improve the results. However, it does not necessarily imply optimal results – the major problem is still one of tractability. In a very large distributed file system where the file system spans a large number of clusters, and where a large number of relevant files exists which should be considered for optimal placement, the size of the problem may still be too high to be solved in a reasonable amount of time.

Description of Scenarios

We distinguish between the scenarios of a Group A and a Group B. The scenarios of Group A differ from those of Group B in the initialization of the file allocation.

- Group A: All program files are fully replicated and distributed among the clusters in the network. There are three replicas of every data file distributed among the clusters 1, 2, 3. Hence, the quorum size for a successful access equals two.
- Group B: All files, program and data, are not replicated. The only replica of the program files is stored at file server n_{43} ; the only replica of the data files is stored at file server n_{21} .

We are also interested in the impact of increasing the workload at the nodes. To answer this question, we study the following cases. Every group of scenarios consists of two single scenarios where the system’s load is varied. A statistical distribution is used to model the program initiations. The initiations of a program p is modeled using an equal distribution with a mean of $\text{MPI}[p]$ seconds, i.e., with an average of $\text{MPI}[p]$ seconds, program p is initiated at one of the nodes.

- Scenarios A.1 and B.1: Programs are initiated once per hour, i.e.,
 $\forall p \in P : \text{MPI}[p] = 3600$
- Scenarios A.2 and B.2: Programs are initiated every 15 minutes, i.e.,
 $\forall p \in P : \text{MPI}[p] = 900$

Due to the increase of the system’s load, the probability for concurrent accesses to the data files increases and the access queues become longer. Consequently, as the workload is increased, the mean program runtimes will be longer.

Measures of Results

For every Strategy (i), $i \in \{1, \dots, 4\}$, we consider the **average runtime** $avru_{(i)}$ for the programs p_1 to p_{30} . The average runtime of the programs is used as performance indicator. Figs. 3–6 illustrate the average runtime measures of the four scenarios. The curves represent the convergence profile for the four strategies. The scale in these figures is logarithmic.

As an additional measurement, we express the strategy-specific relative **profit-and-loss** $pal_{(j)}$ of the Strategies (j), $j \in \{2, 3, 4\}$, for every program. The relative profit-and-loss is derived as a ratio of the difference of the average runtime for the programs of the reference Strategy (1) and the strategy in question to the average runtime for the programs of the reference Strategy (1), i.e.,

$$pal_{(j)} = \frac{avru_{(1)} - avru_{(j)}}{avru_{(1)}}.$$

The observed relative profit-and-loss measures of the Strategies (2), (3), and (4) are plotted in Figs. 7–10.

Discussion of the Results

Since the program initiations are equally distributed in the scenarios of Group A, Strategy (2) is not fit to reduce the average runtime of the programs in Group II and III. We observe that its profit is between -4.4% and 2.8%.

A profit of 6.0% to 8.7% in the scenarios of Group A and a profit of 42.5% to 44.2% in those of Group B, indicates that Strategy (3) is a good candidate in reducing the average runtime of our programs in Group II and III.

You can notice that in some cases the gain in performance is negative, e.g., see the results of Program Group I in Scenario A.1 (Figs. 3 or 7). Using the IPELA in Strategies (3) and (4), leads to an increase of the runtime of the I/O-active programs p_1 to p_{10} . The time consumed in order to calculate their best executing location is out of proportion compared with their runtime.

To conclude, I/O-active programs should always be executed within the initiating cluster. They should never be of interest for the IPELA as long as their size is smaller than the amount of I/O-traffic they are supposed to produce.

Due to the fact that the initiations of the programs are equally distributed, after a few optimizations the CFAP can determine a stabilized, optimal file allocation. Only during a short interval of time, relocation loading is occurred. During the interval where the data files are relocated, the degree of concurrency increases.

Under light load, the performance loss is negligible. Under heavy load we detect poor performance, e.g., program p_{20} has a loss in performance of 130.9%. Its average runtime is more than doubled. Fig. 2 shows the average runtime of the programs during the period of relocation under heavy load conditions. Since the period of relocation is short, just a few programs are initiated.

We use a priority-driven strategy to relocate files [6]. Files are gradually relocated and selected by their size. However, if a designer of a distributed file system can not tolerate such a performance loss – even for a small amount of time – then relocations should be suspended under heavy load conditions. To conclude, the higher the current load in the system the higher is the probability of a performance loss during the period of relocation.

Fig. 2. Average Runtime of Some Programs During the Period of Relocation.

Characteristics of the CFAP

Tab. 2 summarizes the characteristics of the CFAP. It includes

- stabilization of the cluster allocation,
- mean number of candidate checks,
- mean length of the interval of observation,
- mean number of relocations per interval of observation.

Scenario	Allocation stabilized?	Candidate Checks	Interval of Observation (Min.)	Number of Relocations
A.1	yes, after 9 relocations	1000	28	→ 0
A.2	yes, after 6 relocations	1000	7	→ 0
B.1	no	45000	62	6.6
B.2	no	45000	62	14.1

Tab. 2. Characteristics of the CFAP.

In the scenarios of Group A, the CFAP checks a mean of 1000 candidates of cluster allocations, i.e., all combinations where the minimal number of replicas is kept. After 9 and 6 relocations, respectively, an optimal cluster allocation is achieved. The mean length of the corresponding intervals of observation are 28 minutes (under light load) and 7 minutes

(under heavy load), i.e., after 28 minutes in Scenario A.1, the cardinality of the relevant program set has reached the threshold value (7 minutes in Scenario A.2, respectively).

Every new CFAP calculation confirms the optimal allocation. Thus the mean number of relocations per interval of observation tends to zero.

In the scenarios of Group B the size of the problem was large enough to cause no optimal solution to be found. Although a maximum of 45000 candidates of cluster allocations are checked after 62 minutes of CPU-time, the current CFAP implementation could not calculate the optimal file allocation. This results in a mean of 6.6 relocations per interval of observation in Scenario B.1, while the mean number of relocations in Scenario B.2 is 14.1.

Although every new CFAP calculation changed the suboptimal allocation determined so far, the locality of the program executions in the scenario of Group B could be improved.

Tab. 3 shows the ratio of cluster-local program executions of our four strategies.

Scenario	Strategies (1)/(2)	Strategy (3)	Strategy (4)
A.1	100	65	55
A.2	100	66	54
B.1	100	49	57
B.2	100	50	58

Tab. 3. Ratio of Cluster-Local Program Executions (in %).

Strategies (1) and (2) have 100% cluster-local program executions by definition. Often, the data files must be read or written over intercluster links. This results in poor performance, see Figs. 3 and 4.

In contrast to that, Strategy (3) looks for the optimal location of a program execution without changing the file allocation. The IPELA determines in the scenarios of Group A that two third of all program runs are locally started. It is interesting that Strategy (4) has a smaller ratio of cluster-local program executions. In these scenarios, the programs are fully replicated – a remote program start does not cause intercluster traffic. Strategy (4) benefits from the optimal allocation of the data files to the clusters even when more programs are remotely executed. At the remote execution location, the program runs find the data files located in a way such that at least one copy is local and the other necessary copy (remember the quorum size equals 2) is reachable via a fast intercluster link.

Now we have a look to the scenarios of Group B. Although only suboptimal cluster allocations are calculated, Strategy (4) increases the ratio of cluster-local program executions in Scenario B.1 to 57% in comparison to Strategy (3) with 49% (58% in Scenario B.2). In these scenarios, Strategy (4) does support the decisions of the IPELA by providing local replicas of the data files. This improves the performance because the I/O-activities of the programs do not cause intercluster traffic. Regarding the quality of our heuristics, an impressive profit

can be reached. Figs. 9 and 10 illustrate that our suboptimal file allocation improves the performance of a majority of programs, whereas a minority of programs could not be considered by the CFAP. This fact and the precision of the measurements lead to the ups and downs which can be seen in both figures.

6 Summary

In this paper, we have presented a solution for the dynamic file allocation problem as well as an optimization for the individual program executions. We showed how our cluster-based approach, together with the introduction of the relevant program and data sets for the dynamic optimizations, reduce the complexity and the size of the NP-complete problem.

Both algorithms have been proto-typically implemented and have been embedded in a discrete event simulation. A number of experiments executed under various workloads and different program profiles has been discussed. We could show how both optimizations cooperate, and we have evaluated their profit. In a simulation study, we compared the following strategies. (1) start a program at the initiating node, (2) start a program load-balanced in the initiating cluster, (3) start a program load-balanced in the optimal cluster determined through the IPELA. Finally, Strategy (4) starts a new program at a node determined as in (3). In addition, the network-wide program initiations were dynamically recorded through the CFAP, and the file allocation was dynamically changed and optimized. As a first result, we could show that the average runtime of the programs decreases with the degree of optimization. Best results were obtained by Strategies (3) and (4). Under light load, the results of Strategy (4) were excellent even when many relocations are necessary in order to move from the current to the optimal file allocation. Under heavy load, relocations could lead to network congestion. Our results implied that relocations should be suspended as soon as the load exceeds a critical value characteristic for the system. The critical value depends on features of the systems, such as the topology of the network, the bandwidths of the communication links, and the current replication degree. In order to avoid network congestion, we used a priority-driven strategy for the relocation problem of replicated files where files are gradually relocated and selected by their size. This scheme served as a given relocation policy in order to gradually improve the allocation of the program and data files. Finally, pure I/O-active programs, i.e., programs that need input and produce output material, but do not access data files, should be executed at the initiating cluster. Any expensive optimization will increase their average runtime.

The integration of the algorithms into an entire local area distributed file system is still in the process of being developed. The applicability of the techniques proposed in very large systems is doubtful for the CFAP. Even using a cluster approach and file sets relevant for the CFAP optimization, the complexity and the problem size might be too high to calculate an optimum within a reasonable amount of time. In such an environment, we can not predict

how efficient the suboptimal allocations are. To simply extend the length of the interval of observation is rather effective. In very large systems the cluster initiator profile will often change and seldomly become stable. Everything indicates that it makes no sense to calculate an optimal file allocation which is absolutely obsolete.

On the other hand, the IPELA could be used even in very large systems. The exhaustive search for the best location of an individual program execution to minimize the intercluster traffic is manageable and should result in better performance. The complexity of the problem to be solved is only quadratic in the number of clusters. That is, increasing the problem size does not severely influence the benefits of the IPELA.

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Fig. 3. Average Runtime of the Programs in Scenario A.1.

Fig. 4. Average Runtime of the Programs in Scenario A.2.

Fig. 5. Average Runtime of the Programs in Scenario B.1.

Fig. 6. Average Runtime of the Programs in Scenario B.2.

Fig. 7. Profit-and-Loss in Scenario A.1.

Fig. 8. Profit-and-Loss in Scenario A.2.

Fig. 9. Profit-and-Loss in Scenario B.1.

Fig. 10. Profit-and-Loss in Scenario B.2.